

Five reasons why an Arctic Observing Network matters for you and your well-being

1 Anticipating and mitigating the impacts of extreme events and tipping points

The Arctic is warming up to four times faster than the global average, disrupting weather patterns connected to more extreme floods, storms, and heatwaves. Melting sea ice, thawing permafrost, and shrinking ice sheets bring us closer to dangerous thresholds of the natural system with potentially irreversible and catastrophic impacts. An Arctic Observing Network provides the data and knowledge needed for better understanding, accurate forecasts, early warnings, and resilience planning at local to global scales.

2 Improving weather forecasts

European weather is influenced by Arctic climate changes. Warming weakens the contrast between the Arctic and mid-latitudes, slowing the jet stream. By feeding vital data into forecasting systems, an Arctic Observing Network improves accuracy, supporting public safety, health, livelihoods, and energy production.

3 Safeguarding biodiversity and ecosystems

The Arctic is one of the most biodiverse regions on our planet, home to unique species and ecosystems adapted to the cold that are now under pressure from climate change and human activity. An Arctic Observing Network enables monitoring, standardised data collection and collaboration to guide conservation, sustainable resource use, and informed policy decisions - helping protect biodiversity that benefits the Arctic and wider world.

4 Supporting wellbeing, culture and knowledge

About 4 million people live in the Arctic. Working in partnership with Indigenous Knowledge Holders and other Arctic residents, and supporting Indigenous-led observing initiatives, we can utilise the combined power of diverse knowledge systems. This allows the network to foster trust, empower communities, and ensure that decisions reflect diverse perspectives, which in turn strengthens cultural preservation, well-being and sustainable management of resources.

5 Promoting peace and international collaboration.

The Arctic has long been a region of cooperation in science and monitoring. Today, rising tensions and resource competition threaten that stability. Built on collaboration, a unified Arctic Observing Network strengthens relationships across borders, supports international agreements and builds shared capacity to tackle global challenges, while promoting peace and resilience.

Contact us:

Alfred Wegener Institute

Project coordinator

arctic-passion-coord@listserv.dfn.de

GRID-Arendal

Communication focal point

arcticpassion@grida.no

www.arcticpassion.eu

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ARCTIC PASSION

Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems: Implementing Observations for Societal Needs

The Arctic is undergoing rapid environmental, economic, geopolitical and societal changes with global consequences. Rising temperatures, wildfires, and ice loss have become the new norm, reinforcing the region's reputation as a climate change hotspot and a warning sign for the planet. Though remote, the Arctic's transformations affect us all.

To respond to these changes, we need to monitor the environment continuously; consequently, a well-coordinated Arctic-wide environmental observing network is essential. Such a network gathers vital data to monitor environmental shifts, assess impacts, help to better understand the natural system and its interaction with humans and supports evidence-based decision-making. While many nations already conduct many of these observations, efforts are often fragmented and need better integration and coordination on many levels.

Arctic PASSION, a project funded by the EU and Canada, brings together scientific and Indigenous experts from 17 countries to improve coordination, relevance and long-term sustainability of such an Arctic observing network.

This factsheet highlights five reasons why a stronger Arctic observing network matters to you, and shares key messages from our work that aim for a further improved Arctic observing network.

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Key messages

Access to an environmental observing network for the Arctic is essential for informed decision-making.

The Arctic's complex and rapidly changing environment requires a thorough understanding of the atmosphere, ocean, ice, land, and ecosystems, as well as how people interact with these components. A cohesive, comprehensive and accessible network that brings together a large number of observations is essential. Data from this network will provide the information necessary for Arctic and non-Arctic societies to make decisions based on the best available knowledge.

Sustainable funding is crucial for a long-term observational network.

Long-term observations provide continuous data essential for detecting trends, understanding change and assessing climate change impacts. These measurements are vital for the understanding of the Arctic environment and its role for the globe, the development of services for users, informed decision-making, and the well-being of the Arctic region and its people.

Arctic observing needs a more holistic, systemic approach and a full inclusion of different knowledge systems.

Indigenous Knowledge and science are distinct but equally valuable knowledge systems. Together, they provide a fuller picture of Arctic environmental change. By understanding the broader context and potential impacts of environmental changes and human actions, societies can develop more effective strategies for adaptation and resilience.

Arctic PASSION efforts to address this

Increasing integration and coordination:

Arctic PASSION has significantly enhanced Arctic environmental observations by fostering better-integrated and coordinated programs. Key achievements include the formation of an Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ArORA) and a Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO) in the Atlantic Arctic, along with support for the terrestrial network INTERACT and the Sustained Arctic Observing Networks (SAON).

Recommendations Towards a Sustained Arctic Observing Network:

In collaboration with the Arctic Science Funders Forum, Arctic PASSION has developed key recommendations for a sustainable Arctic observing network. These include establishing long-term coordinating bodies and monitoring systems for consistent data collection, enhancing research station networks for better data accessibility, knowledge exchange, and advocating for inclusive and equitable funding to enable participation of Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents.

Indigenous-led repositories of climate and ecological change:

Arctic PASSION has been favoured with the trust of Indigenous Peoples from eight Arctic communities to co-create a unique database (<https://arcticseas.org/>), composed of Indigenous Knowledge, scientific findings, historic sources, archival data and observations, thus pushing the boundaries of knowledge and collaboration. It includes previously unreleased Indigenous Knowledge, consented by the knowledge holders, that can now be used to understand the Arctic change more holistically.

Partner Organisations

Partner communities

- Inuvialuit
- Khanty, Mansi
- Chukchi, Even, Yukaghir, Dolgan
- Fróðskaparsetrið
- Tahltan
- Gwich'in
- Inuit
- Inupiaq and Yupiaq
- Skolt, Ter and Kildin Sami

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An agreed and enforceable framework for harmonised and interoperable data following FAIR and CARE principles, as well as respecting Indigenous Data sovereignty, is essential.

Access to data is at the heart of any observing network. Information must be accessible to everyone: to scientists, policymakers, Indigenous Peoples, the private sector and the public. This fosters transparency, trust, accountability, and public engagement. Ethical and equitable data use is vital, respecting the rights and values of Indigenous Peoples (as outlined in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples), as well as local communities, to facilitate shared understanding and collective action.

The observing network components must meet the needs of a wide variety of user groups, including Arctic inhabitants, academia, public and private sectors, and decision-makers.

Different user groups have distinct needs and priorities. Some may require information on ice conditions for safe travel, while others might need detailed climate predictions. Involving, e.g. Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents in the design, implementation and use of the observing network ensures an equal knowledge transfer and that their needs and concerns are considered. This engagement empowers communities. Tailoring the observing network ensures that the data collected is relevant and usable for the specific groups, enhancing its value and applicability.

Arctic PASSION efforts to address this

Bringing the Arctic data system into action:

Arctic PASSION has strengthened the Arctic data system through various improvements, including harmonisation and the development of a web interface for standardisation. It has developed recommendations to improve data provision from the Copernicus service and the Copernicus Arctic Hub. These efforts enhance data access and unify standards, helping to make data machine-readable and interoperable.

Development of new information services:

Arctic PASSION has combined data from different international observation programmes with local Arctic data and Indigenous Knowledge to create eight new information services. These services are designed to address specific needs such as air pollution forecasting, wildfire information and management, state of the Arctic environment, shipping safety, lake ice thickness and improved permafrost monitoring. These services are co-created with Indigenous Peoples, other Arctic residents, and decision-makers to ensure they are relevant and useful.

